

Interpersonal, Leadership and Supervisory Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in Relation to Teachers' Performance

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Abstract:

This study investigated the the levels of interpersonal, leadership and supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads in relation to teachers' performance of one of the districts of a medium size division in Central Philippines for the School Year 2020-2021. The study made use of descriptive analytical research design, and used a self-made questionnaire which was fully validated and reliability tested. The study utilized 129 teachers sampled out from a population of 192. The level of interpersonal skills of public elementary School Heads was high in both communication skills and emotional intelligence and very high in decision making and problem-solving. The level of leadership skills of public elementary School Heads was very high in the pursuance of mission and vision and on high level for both empowering teachers and collaboration with the community. The level of supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads was very high in written and oral communication, and both on high level in the area of conflict resolution and mentorship. The level of teachers' performance was very satisfactory. The comparative analysis revealed the following: there was a significant difference in the level of inter personal skills of public elementary School Heads when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables; there was a significant difference in the level of leadership skills of public elementary School Heads when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables; there was a significant difference in the level of supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables; there was no significant relationship between the level of interpersonal skills of public elementary School Heads and level of teachers' performance; there was no significant relationship between the level of leadership skills of public elementary School Heads and level of teachers' performance.

Keywords: School Heads, interpersonal skills, leadership skills, supervisory skills, teachers' performance

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Every school or school cluster is led by a school head who is selected, trained, supported, monitored, and accountable for the organization and leading of an institutionalized school improvement process at the school level," according to section E of Republic Act 9155, also known as the Governance of Basic Education. This requirement explicitly outlined the duties of the school head, and the legislation gives school leaders additional authority to guide teachers and students to attain high-quality learning outcomes (Panol et al., 2020).

The ability of the school head to influence teachers and school operations through good communication is essentially referred to as interpersonal skills. Their ability to communicate effectively and command attention through speeches and communications helps to build a school culture, promote educational initiatives that enhance learning, and advance professional growth (Wahed, 2015).

Every school's success or failure can be attributed to the leadership abilities of its administrators. Every school head becomes an educational manager and an efficient administrator planner as a result of this work (Wenceslao, 2018).

The supervisory abilities of school heads enable teachers to focus on teaching-learning activities and ensure that their opinions are acknowledged when decisions are being made. One of the most important abilities is instructional monitoring, which will guarantee that students receive high-quality instruction and that teachers have a comfortable environment in which to teach (Wenceslao, 2018).

As a school principal, the researcher has observed some degree of disparity in the achievements of schools in her district. Could this be an issue with the interpersonal, leadership and supervisory skills of the school heads or is it a

built-in obsolescence in the system? It is also her observation that some of the most critically important issues in school are often left unresolved because there are school heads who are unable to convey the right message to their subordinates. Others are unable to keep up with the desired instructional supervisory requirements thereby affecting the over-all academic standing of the learners. These observations are real and these motivated the researcher in conducting this study.

Current State of Knowledge

School Heads are tasked with the responsibility in improving teachers' plight, personal or career-wise. However, due to lack of time, some School Heads fail to carry out this task effectively. For example, classroom visitation which is considered as a significant component for teacher development, as often sidelined due to a lengthy process. Using School Heads limited time to improve teachers plight becomes an issue (Westerberg, 2013).

Furthermore, School Principals are expected to lay down the foundation for the standards of community interaction among staffs, faculty and the community. They serve as bridge between the education system, students, teachers and parents. School heads play a significant role in putting meaning the school's atmosphere and culture while influencing the faculty's attitude towards their students. With a successful principal, a school can be a welcoming place where students not only learn but are also challenged, encouraged and supported. School principals must have strong interpersonal skills to lead effectively.

School Heads ability to communicate effectively is crucial in the implementation of school programs as these facilitates rapid information exchange between and among school officials, teachers, students, among others. As school managers, these skills define effective leadership. (Ahlaini, 2021).

School leaders that are effective in communicating must have the same ability to build strong relationships, resolve conflicts and the ability to empower teachers by delegating some important obligations. It's a daunting but all-too-common sight for many teachers: A classroom full of rowdy students who are unable to focus on the lesson. Classroom management techniques may get things back on track, but valuable time has already been lost. Many experienced teachers know that making meaningful connections with students is one of the most effective ways to prevent disruptions in the first place, and a new study set out to assess this approach. In classrooms where teachers used a series of techniques centered around establishing, maintaining, and restoring relationships, academic engagement increased by 33 percent and disruptive behavior decreased by 75 percent—making the time students spent in the classroom more worthwhile and productive (Terada, 2019).

According to Garrison and Ehringhaus (2019), giving students descriptive feedback while they are learning is one of the most important ways to involve them in the evaluation of their own learning. Descriptive feedback is actually the most effective teaching method for advancing pupils' learning, according to study. Students receive descriptive feedback that helps them understand their strengths, makes connections to what they have learned in class, and offers precise advice on how to advance to the next stage of the learning process. Descriptive feedback is not a grade, a sticker, or a "good job!" According to a substantial body of research, students do not learn more when they receive this kind of limited feedback.

A relevant study by Tizon (2019) examined senior high school teachers' perceived level of communication skills and teaching performance. The study found that teachers rated themselves as having superior communication skills, while school heads and students perceived them as outstanding in teaching performance. Interestingly, the study revealed no significant relationship between communication skills and teaching performance, suggesting that while effective communication is essential, other factors such as pedagogical strategies and classroom management also contribute to overall effectiveness.

In 2021, Ahlaini conducted a study on the effectiveness of interpersonal communications skills of the school principals in Indonesia. This research uses compare journals related to the effectiveness of interpersonal communication in the sphere of education. Based on the results of a literature review from various countries in the world, the authors found that interpersonal communication can help the school principal in carrying out their duties by communicating in interpersonal with anyone. Therefore, the principal is expected to communicate well in interpersonal to create relationships, openness and trust within the scope of the organization Communication that can be done by the principal is interpersonal communication to create the relationship and trust are invited to communicate. Interpersonal communication can be effective if communication is conducted face-to-front and two-way with openness, clarity, transparency, brief, kindness, concrete, consideration. The importance of the effectiveness of interpersonal communication in education attracts researcher to examine, and this article is to test how the effectiveness of interpersonal communication of the principal in the organization.

A study by Gutiérrez-Cobo et al. (2019) examined the ability emotional intelligence (EI) of head teachers compared to other school personnel. The study found that head teachers exhibited significantly higher EI scores, particularly in the understanding branch of emotional intelligence, compared to teachers in other positions. The findings suggest

that school leaders require strong emotional competencies to manage daily challenges, foster effective communication, and support teachers and students. This aligns with your results, where school heads demonstrated high levels of emotional intelligence, particularly in listening and comprehension skills.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is grounded on these theories: the Agency Theory by Stephen Ross and Barry Mitnick (1973) to account for the school heads' financial management skills and the Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) Theory (Graen & Uhl-Bien, 1995). The Agency Theory is an economic theory that examines the relationship between a principal and an agent, and how to align their financial interests. The theory is often applied to corporate finance, governance, and management. The main concept of this theory talks about the Principal and the Agent, whereby, the principal is the owner of a company, while the agent is the person who manages the company. For example, shareholders are the principal and corporate directors are the agent. Agency theory argues that a company's value can't be maximized if the agent isn't properly incentivized or monitored.

Agency theory explains how conflicts of interest can arise between the principal and agent, and how to resolve them. For example, a company executive might want to expand into a new, high-risk market, but shareholders might be concerned about the long-term risk. Companies can use mechanisms like auditing and board oversight to realign the interests of the principal and agent.

There is a similar grounding scenario between school heads and school officials where the decision-maker (school heads) may take resource distribution to a different direction apart from what other subordinates or officials may want to. However, regardless of the differences in the opinion of school officials as to where or how resources are allocated, accountability and oversight functions may still align their interests based on the school's mission and vision. This theory works well in explaining how school heads are likely manage school resources.

This theory highlights the quality of relationships between leaders and their subordinates, emphasizing how strong, trust-based interactions between school heads and teachers can influence performance. In the context of school heads' financial management practices and skills in relation to teachers' performance, LMX Theory provides valuable insights into how financial leadership impacts teacher effectiveness.

Furthermore, the theory posits that high-quality leader-member relationships enable effective financial decision-making, ensuring that teachers have access to necessary instructional resources, professional development, and incentives. When school heads foster positive exchanges with teachers, they can better prioritize budgeting decisions that enhance teaching effectiveness and job satisfaction. According to LMX Theory, strong leader-member exchanges result in mutual trust and open communication. If school heads demonstrate accountability and transparency in financial management, teachers are more likely to feel confident in institutional policies, fostering a stable teaching environment.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the levels of School Heads financial management practices and skills in relation to the level of teacher's performance in a cluster of a medium-sized schools divisions in central Philippines for School Year 2024-2025. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions: 1) determine the profile of the respondents in terms of Age, Highest Educational Attainment and Length of Service; 2) determine the level of the level of interpersonal skills of public elementary School Heads in terms of Communications Skills, Emotional Intelligence, and Decision making and problem solving, 3) determine the level of leadership skills of public elementary School Heads in terms Pursuance of Mission and Vision, Empowering Teachers, and Collaboration with the community; 4) determine the level of supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads in terms of Written and Verbal communication, Conflict resolution, and Mentorship; 5) determine the level of teachers' performance; 6) determine if there is a significant difference in the level of interpersonal skills of public elementary School Heads when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables; 7) determine if there is significant difference in the level of leadership skills of public elementary School Heads when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables; 8) determine if there is a significant difference in the level of supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables; 9) determine if there is a significant relationship between the level of interpersonal skills of public elementary School Heads and level of teachers' performance; 10) determine if there is a significant relationship between the level of interpersonal skills of public elementary School Heads and level of teachers' performance; and 11) determine if there is a significant relationship between the level of supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads and level of teachers' performance.

Methodology:

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

This study used descriptive research design to determine the level of levels of interpersonal, leadership and supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads in relation to teachers' performance in the Division of Kabankalan City for the School Year 2020-2021.

Descriptive research design is valuable in providing facts in which scientific judgment maybe based on assessing the present study. Furthermore, a descriptive design is appropriate for studies which aims to find out what prevails in the present conditions or relationships, held opinions and beliefs, processes and effects, and developing trends. This research design is a scientific method which involves observing and describing the behavior of a subject without influencing it in any way (Carlson, 2018).

This research design is considered appropriate for this particular study because its purpose was to find out the level of School Heads' interpersonal, leadership and supervisory skills in relation to Teachers' Performance. It is the nature of this study to assess the condition of things in their present state. Likewise, it delves into the relationship among variables that are considered in the study as well as the influence of one variable to another.

Study Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 129 out of 193 public elementary school teachers who are officially teaching in one of the districts of a medium-sized division in Central Philippines. Since the number of respondents is quite large to handle, stratified random sampling technique was used and Cochran formula was used to find the sample size. The respondents were randomly selected by the researcher from each School Level using the lottery technique.

Instruments

To determine the level of school heads' interpersonal, leadership and supervisory skills in relation to teachers' performance, this study made use of a self-made data gathering instrument which was subjected to Validity Test (4.87 - excellent) and Reliability testing (0.806, interpreted as good; For leadership, it was 0.827, interpreted as good; and for the supervisory, it was 0.744, interpreted as acceptable). The questionnaire consisted of two parts: Part 1 gathered the respondents' socio-economic information, such as Age, Highest Educational Attainment and Length of Service. Part 2 contained a total of 63 line-items. There were 21-line items for each of the major area namely interpersonal skills, leadership skills, supervisory skills.

Data Gathering Procedure

Prior to the collection of data, a formal letter asking permission to conduct the study was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent. That letter provided the SDO and the SDS a proper heads-up as to the purpose of the study, when and how the study will be conducted. The data gathering instrument was administered after the approval was secured and the copies of the instrument were retrieved after 3days After the collection of data, they were organized for statistical interpretation.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 utilized descriptive analytical scheme and employed Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of Age, Highest Educational Attainment and Length of Service.

Objective No. 2 also used descriptive analytical scheme and utilized Mean as its statistical tool to determine the level of the level of interpersonal skills of public elementary School Heads in terms of Communications Skills, Emotional Intelligence, and Decision making and problem solving.

Objective No. 3 still used descriptive analytical scheme and utilized Mean as its statistical tool to determine the level of leadership skills of public elementary School Heads in terms of Pursuance of Mission and Vision, Empowering Teachers, and Collaboration with the community.

Objective No. 4 also used descriptive analytical scheme and utilized Mean as its statistical tool to determine the level of supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads in terms of Written and Verbal communication, Conflict resolution, and Mentorship.

Objective No. 5 used descriptive analytical scheme and utilized Mean as its statistical tool to determine the level of teachers' performance.

Objective No. 6 used comparative analytical scheme and utilized Mann-Whitney U Test to determine if there is a significant difference in the level of interpersonal skills of public elementary School Heads when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 7 also used comparative analytical scheme to determine if there is a significant difference in the level of leadership skills of public elementary School Heads when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 8 still used comparative analytical scheme to determine if there is a significant difference in the level of supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 9 used relational analysis to determine if there is a significant relationship between the level of interpersonal skills of public elementary School Heads and level of teachers' performance.

Objective No. 10 used relational analysis to determine if there is a significant relationship between the level of leadership skills of public elementary School Heads and level of teachers' performance.

Objective No. 11 used relational analysis to determine if there is a significant relationship between the level of supervisory skills of public elementary School Heads and level of teachers' performance.

Ethical Consideration

This study made sure that key ethical principles were strictly followed throughout the duration of the study. These included providing the respondents with the necessary information to make a determination as to whether they want to be part of the study. The signing of the consent form, which is actually a process rather than an event was not used as coercive tool to compel participants to complete the study. They were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any point when they became uncomfortable with the study. The identity of the children as well as their responses was kept confidential such that neither the responses nor their identity was revealed to any other person outside the research team.

Results and Discussion:

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Profile of the Respondents According to Age, Highest Educational Attainment and Length of Service

Table 1
Profile of Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (Below 38 years old)	74	57.40
	Older (38 years old and above)	55	42.60
	Total	129	100.00
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower (Bachelors' Degree)	96	74.40
	Higher (Masters/Doctorate)	33	25.60
	Total	129	100.00
Length of Service	Shorter (Less than 10 years)	71	55.00
	Longer (10 years or more)	58	45.00
	Total	129	100.00

In terms of age, there were 74 or 57.40% younger (below 38 years old) respondents and 55 or 42.60% older (38 years old and above) respondents. In terms of highest educational attainment, there were 96 or 74.40% who belong to the lower group and 33 or 25.60% belonged to higher group. In terms of length of service, there were 71 or 55.00%, Also, shorter tenure in service (less than 10 years) group and 58 or 45.00% longer tenure in service (10 years and more) group.

This implies that majority of the respondents belong to the younger category and most of the respondents have no post graduate degrees. In terms of their length of service, majority of the respondents belong to the shorter or less tenured groups.

Level of Interpersonal Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in Communication Skills, Emotional Intelligence and Decision Making and Problem Solving

Table 2
Level of Interpersonal Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in the Area Communication Skills

Items	Mean	Interpretation
The School Head ...		
1. can clearly communicate to everyone.	4.10	High Level
2. can send his/her message across all concerns effectively.	4.57	Very High Level
3. has a very organized thought in talking.	4.26	High Level
4. provides examples when stressing a point.	4.16	High Level
5. discusses pros and cons of every issue being decided on.	4.14	High Level
6. creates open communication lines for everyone.	4.19	High Level
7. is open for suggestion at all times.	3.43	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	4.12	High Level

The overall mean score was 4.12, interpreted as "high level". Item No. 2 which states "The school Head can send his/her message across all concerns effectively" got the highest mean score of 4.57, interpreted as "very high level", while Item No. 7 which states "The school Head is open for suggestion at all times" got the lowest mean score of 3.43, interpreted as "moderate level".

This means that there are school heads who are not very often open to discuss matters with suggestions from subordinates. There could be varying reasons for this. One is that, crucial matters may be needing the School Head's decision. Another reason could be at times, when a subject matter is open for suggestion and discussions, matters get worse because quarrels among subordinates may spark and leads to further division.

A relevant study by Tizon (2019) examined senior high school teachers' perceived level of communication skills and teaching performance. The study found that teachers rated themselves as having superior communication skills, while school heads and students perceived them as outstanding in teaching performance. Interestingly, the study revealed no significant relationship between communication skills and teaching performance, suggesting that while effective communication is essential, other factors such as pedagogical strategies and classroom management also contribute to overall effectiveness.

Table 3
Level of Interpersonal Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in the Area Emotional Intelligence

Items	Mean	Interpretation
The School Head ...		
1. has the ability to listen when someone explains.	4.49	High Level
2. has the ability to understand while listening.	3.53	High Level
3. creates opportunities for everyone to air his opinion while he/she listens.	3.77	High Level
4. encourages everyone to speak while he/she is carefully listening.	4.64	Very High Level
5. never interrupts anybody who is speaking while he/she listens.	4.51	Very High Level
6. encourages everyone to find time to listen instead of talking.	4.62	Very High Level

7. shows higher comprehension and objectivity with all things he/she hears.	4.63	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.31	High Level

The overall mean score was 4.31, interpreted as "high level". Item No. 4 which states that "School Heads encourages everyone to speak while he/she is carefully listening" got the highest mean score of 4.64, interpreted as "very high level", while Item No. 2 which states that "School Heads has the ability to understand while listening" got the lowest mean score of 3.53, interpreted as "high level".

This result shows that there are few school heads who may not really be good at listening or those who are not sensitive to the opinion and suggestions of their subordinates. Most often, this relates to personality of individual school heads. However, this may create an impression that some sectors are being canceled or excluded from bigger school issues. A relevant study by Gutiérrez-Cobo et al. (2019) examined the ability emotional intelligence (EI) of head teachers compared to other school personnel. The study found that head teachers exhibited significantly higher EI scores, particularly in the understanding branch of emotional intelligence, compared to teachers in other positions. The findings suggest that school leaders require strong emotional competencies to manage daily challenges, foster effective communication, and support teachers and students.

Table 4
Level of Interpersonal Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in the Area Decision Making and Problem Solving

Items	Mean	Interpretation
The School Head ...		
1. discusses issues on the table with all stakeholders.	4.81	Very High Level
2. allows all parties to participate in all deliberations to easily decide or resolve issues.	3.91	High Level
3. provides proper forum for all concern to discuss school issues that affects them.	4.76	Very High Level
4. objectively considers all sides in every issue when making decisions.	4.64	Very High Level
5. remains calm with a well-organized thought when solving any problem.	4.73	Very High Level
6. presents the issue to the body from a neutral standpoint.	4.88	Very High Level
7. provides new insights on all school issues.	4.71	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.63	Very High Level

The overall mean score was 4.63, interpreted as "very high level". Item No. 6 which states "presents the issue to the body from a neutral standpoint" got the highest mean score of 4.88, interpreted as "very high level", while Item No. 2 which states "allows all parties to participate in all deliberations to easily decide or resolve issues" got the lowest mean score of 3.91, interpreted as "high level".

This implies that there a number of school heads who are less collaborative in providing answers to school issues. This means that on some occasions, participative decision-making is not followed. Although the School Heads have inherent powers to decide on their own, it has been a collegial practice to involve other stakeholders in most decision making.

Very often, when stakeholders are involved, they feel empowered and counted. Silva (2019) examined the decision-making practices of school heads in Batangas and found that effective leadership is strongly linked to structured decision-making processes. The study highlighted that school heads who engage stakeholders, maintain neutrality, and provide forums for discussion tend to foster better school management and instructional leadership.

Level of Leadership Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in the Pursuance of Mission and Vision, Empowering Teachers and Collaboration with the Community

Table 5
Level of Leadership Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in the Pursuance of Mission and Vision

Items	Mean	Interpretation
The School Head ...		
1. ensures that teachers are involved in major school activities through responsibility sharing.	4.60	Very High Level

2. consults teachers before making decisions that could impact their lives as educators.	4.50	Very High Level
3. looks after the over-all welfare of the teachers.	4.53	Very High Level
4. encourages teachers to take post graduate studies.	4.43	High Level
5. helps teachers in looking for scholarship grants to pursue higher education.	4.46	High Level
6. sends teachers to trainings and workshops to improve teaching competencies.	4.43	High Level
7. assigns appropriate tasks to teachers in school.	4.51	Very High Level
Overall Mean	4.50	Very High Level

The overall mean score was 4.50, interpreted as “very high level”. Item No. 1 which states “School Heads ensures that teachers are involved in major school activities through responsibility sharing” got the highest mean score of 4.60, interpreted as “very high level”, while Item Nos. 4 and 6 which states “encourages teachers to take post graduate studies” and “sends teachers to trainings and workshops to improve teaching competencies” got the lowest mean score of 4.43, interpreted as “high level”.

This implies that some of the school heads are less active in encouraging the teachers to pursue masters or doctorate degrees or send them to other trainings meant to upskill teachers and improve their pedagogical capabilities. One of the main reasons for this would be the budgetary limitations of some public schools. However, for those who wanted to pursue additional post graduate studies, School Heads may refer the teachers to the City Scholarship or private scholarships fundings. It is important that school heads serve as primary movers for the teachers to pursue further studies.

A relevant study by Aquino et al. (2021) examined school heads' leadership practices and their impact on teacher performance in public schools. The study found that strong leadership skills, particularly in fostering teacher involvement and professional development, significantly enhance school effectiveness.

Table 6
Level of Leadership Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in Empowering Teachers

Items	Mean	Interpretation
The School Head ...		
1. works hard to achieve school objectives and its mission.	4.41	High Level
2. encourages teachers to be their best to provide quality education.	4.41	High Level
3. reminds teachers and learners to focus on the school’s mission and vision.	4.32	High Level
4. teaches teachers on how to help achieve the school’s primary goals.	3.19	Moderate Level
5. repeatedly informs teachers to be proactive in achieving academic excellence.	3.39	Moderate Level
6. exerts efforts to make sure that teaching and learning experiences are on higher levels.	4.53	Very High Level
7. emphasizes quality teaching to achieve higher academic goals.	4.45	High Level
Overall Mean	4.10	High Level

The overall mean score was 4.10, interpreted as “high level”. Item No. 6 which states “School Heads exerts efforts to make sure that teaching and learning experiences are on higher levels” got the highest mean score of 4.53, interpreted as “very high level”, while Item No. 4 which states “School Heads teaches teachers on how to help achieve the school’s primary goals” got the lowest mean score of 3.19, interpreted as “moderate level”.

The result of the study clearly stated that there are school heads who are less attentive to the needs to assist teachers, especially the new ones, on how to help teachers achieve academic excellence. This result does not summarize the over-all actuation of the school heads, perhaps only a few. There is a need to give credit also to school heads who are attentive and religiously assisting their subordinate teachers. Given ample time and resources, school heads will be able to perform well in their positions.

This was concurred by Ignace (2015) who stated that educational management involves the application of management values and skills in designing, developing and effecting resources towards achievement of educational goals. The effective coordination in management is of great potentialities for provision of quality secondary education.

Various studies asserted that the overall responsibility for a school's head is conflicts management in school. The more closely people are expected to work together, the more the possibility of conflict to rise.

Table 7

Level of Leadership Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in Collaboration with the Community

Items	Mean	Interpretation
The School Head ...		
1. promotes collaborative works with the barangays.	4.43	High Level
2. creates opportunities for the school and community to collaborate in teaching out of school youth.	4.29	High Level
3. encourages teachers and learners to do volunteer community works.	4.35	High Level
4. works with the school PTA to help provide simple community needs.	4.49	High Level
5. creates various school programs that help impact community relations.	4.51	Very High Level
6. taps school benefactors and the alumni to help with community services.	4.28	High Level
7. actively provides support for the ALS program.	4.14	High Level
Overall Mean	4.36	High Level

The overall mean score was 4.36, interpreted as "high level". Item No. 5 which states "creates various school programs that help impact community relations" got the highest mean score of 4.51, interpreted as "very high level", while Item No. 7 which states "actively provides support for the ALS program" got the lowest mean score of 4.17, interpreted as "high level".

The result showed that there are school heads who are less supportive of the ALS Program, not all but only a small portion. This can be associated with the fact that attention-wise, school heads are already very much loaded normal school routine while ALS coordination in some schools are added works for them. The need to properly educate the school heads on the importance of this program is highly important. Garrison and Ehringhaus (2019), said that one of the key components of engaging students in the assessment of their own learning is providing them with descriptive feedback as they learn.

In fact, research shows descriptive feedback to be the most significant instructional strategy to move students forward in their learning. Descriptive feedback provides students with an understanding of what they are doing well, links to classroom learning, and gives specific input on how to reach the next step in the learning progression. In other words, descriptive feedback is not a grade, a sticker, or "good job!" A significant body of research indicates that such limited feedback does not lead to improved student learning.

Level of Supervisory Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in the Areas, Written and Verbal Communication, Conflict Resolution and Mentorship

Table 8

Level of Supervisory Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in the Area Written and Verbal Communication

Items	Mean	Interpretation
The School Head ...		
1. creates opportunities to improve teachers' pedagogical competencies.	4.61	Very High Level
2. ensures that learners receive quality education.	4.64	Very High Level
3. takes time to discuss learning resource materials.	4.64	Very High Level
4. finds time to randomly check instructional materials used by teachers.	4.53	Very High Level
5. discusses with teachers new teaching approaches.	4.51	Very High Level
6. provides constructive criticisms on how to effectively handle the class based on CO results.	4.23	High Level
7. encourages teachers to utilize ICT-based instruction to improve teaching-learning experiences.	4.33	High Level
Overall Mean	4.50	Very High Level

The overall mean score was 4.50, interpreted as “very high level”. Item Nos. 2 and 3 which states “ensures that learners receive quality education” and “takes time to discuss learning resource materials” got the highest mean score of 4.64, interpreted as “very high level”, while Item No. 6 which states “provides constructive criticisms on how to effectively handle the class based on CO results” got the lowest mean score of 4.23, interpreted as “high level”. This result revealed that some school heads have issues providing constructive criticisms or feedback to teachers such as post-classroom observation activity.

This is indicative of the fact that not all SH’s are well trained in intra-personal communication. The school heads with effective communication skills, must have the ability to build strong relationships, resolve conflicts and the ability to empower teachers by delegating some important obligations. It’s a daunting but all-too-common sight for many teachers: A classroom full of rowdy students who are unable to focus on the lesson. Classroom management techniques may get things back on track, but valuable time has already been lost. Many experienced teachers know that making meaningful connections with students is one of the most effective ways to prevent disruptions in the first place, and a new study set out to assess this approach. In classrooms where teachers used a series of techniques centered around establishing, maintaining, and restoring relationships, academic engagement increased by 33 percent and disruptive behavior decreased by 75 percent—making the time students spent in the classroom more worthwhile and productive (Terada, 2019).

Table 9
Level of Supervisory Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in the Area Conflict Resolution

Items	Mean	Interpretation
The School Head ...		
1. knows how to put priorities in their proper perspective,	4.23	High Level
2. prioritizes academic needs over other priorities.	4.51	Very High Level
3. keeps operational needs in place without sacrificing academic concerns.	4.40	High Level
4. consults all departments about their respective priorities.	4.23	High Level
5. sets priorities based on agreed terms with all concern groups.	4.46	High Level
6. involves stake holders in validating the annual list of priority projects in school.	4.29	High Level
7. creates opportunities for all benefactors to help in funding priority programs like teachers’ training.	4.09	High Level
Overall Mean	4.32	High Level

The overall mean score was 4.32, interpreted as “high level”. Item No. 2 which states “prioritizes academic needs over other priorities” got the highest mean score of 4.51, interpreted as “very high level”, while Item No. 7 which states “creates opportunities for all benefactors to help in funding priority programs like teachers’ training” got the lowest mean score of 4.07, interpreted as “high level”. This reveals the need for the school heads to identify specific school programs where benefactors can easily fit-in. This may require proper matching, to what project each benefactor may be able to help. This may not be done alone but with the help of other stakeholders. This was supported by Kalagbor & Nnokam (2015) who stated that Conflict resolution involves the reduction, elimination, or termination of all forms and types of conflicts. Hence, conflict resolution tends to use terms like negotiation, bargaining, mediation or arbitration. While conflict management is a method incorporated to facilitate a positive or at least an agreeable outcome. Principals and teachers do involve in conflict resolution and management in the school system on issues bordering on students’ discipline and control.

Table 10
Level of Supervisory Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in the Area Mentorship

Items	Mean	Interpretation
The School Head ...		
1. allows teachers to go on study leave.	4.29	High Level
2. encourages teachers to take higher education/studies.	4.36	High Level
3. helps teachers in looking for sponsors for their competency and skills trainings.	4.16	High Level
4. connects teachers with LGU for possible scholarship grants for post graduate studies.	4.59	Very High Level

5. allows teachers to conduct studies related to their field.	4.44	High Level
6. encourages teachers to conduct action research studies in school.	4.38	High Level
7. encourages teachers to take steps towards job promotions.	4.31	High Level
Overall Mean	4.36	High Level

The overall mean score was 4.36, interpreted as "high level". Item No. 4 which states "connects teachers with LGU for possible scholarship grants for post graduate studies" got the highest mean score of 4.59, interpreted as "very high level", while Item No. 3 which states "helps teachers in looking for sponsors for their competency and skills trainings" got the lowest mean score of 4.16, interpreted as "high level". This reveals the fact that there are teachers who are not fully convinced that their school heads are doing their best to support their competency skills training, as such, some teachers believed that the efforts of the school heads in seeking external support for such trainings must be increased. This was supported by Busico (2020) conducted a study on the instructional competence and supervisory skills of School Heads in relation to teachers' performance in one of the districts of a large-size division in Negros Oriental. The result of the study showed that School Head's Instructional Competence and Supervisory Skills were all on high level. The result of the study showed that some school heads are unable manage everyone's expectations on certain school projects and undertakings which means that they are unable to communicate properly with stakeholders.

Level of Teachers' Performance during the School Year 2020-2021

Table 11

Level of Teachers' Performance

Item	Mean	Interpretation
Teachers' Performance	4.33	Very Satisfactory

The teacher's performance obtained a mean score of 4.33, interpreted as "very satisfactory". This means that there is still a greater room for improvement for teachers' performance. With proper support from school heads, with more opportunities for teachers to take lead roles, they will be able to reach outstanding rating. Ultimately, any teacher can be a leader, even in a small regard. Anytime someone steps up to make decision, implement an idea, or just share an example of making a better impact on their students, they are a teacher leader. Every organization needs strong leadership to function. But also, many organizations have a stratification that separates the top-level decision makers from the ground-level workers. This is especially true in schools, when administrators have often not taught in the classroom in years and have questionable insights into the needs of their teachers. (Catapano, 2017).

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Interpersonal Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in the Areas, Communication Skills, Emotional Intelligence and Decision Making and Problem Solving when grouped and compared according to the Variables, Age, Highest Educational Attainment and Length of Service

Table 12

Difference in the Level of Interpersonal Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in the Area Communication Skills According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	74	64.24	1979.000	0.789		Not Significant
	Older	55	66.02				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	96	65.42	1543.500	0.826	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	33	63.77				
Length of Service	Shorter	71	63.61	1960.500	0.640		Not Significant
	Longer	58	66.70				

When grouped according to age, highest educational attainment, and length of service, the computed p -values were higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as “not significant”. Thus, the hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference in the level of interpersonal skills of public elementary school heads in the area communication skills according to age, highest educational attainment and length of service” was therefore “accepted”. This implies that age, highest educational attainment and length of service does not affect the level of interpersonal skills of public elementary school heads in terms of communication skills. This equally means that teachers have a uniform opinion on school heads communication skills. This was supported by the study of Cusi (2020) on the supervisory and financial management skills of public elementary school heads in relation to teachers’ performance in a large size division in Central Negros Occidental. In terms of communication, the result of the study showed that some school heads are unable manage everyone’s expectations on certain school projects and undertakings which means that they are unable to communicate properly with stakeholders. Teachers’ performance was at very satisfactory level. There were no significant differences between School Heads supervisory skills and also with their financial management skills if correlated with teachers’ performance. There was also no significant relationship between School Heads’ supervisory skills and teachers’ performance and no significant relationship between school heads’ financial management skills and teachers’ performance.

Table 13
Difference in the Level of Interpersonal Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in the Area Emotional Intelligence According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	74	66.70	1909.500	0.547		Not Significant
	Older	55	62.72				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	96	70.59	1047.000	0.003	0.05	Significant
	Higher	33	48.73				
Length of Service	Shorter	71	68.51	1809.500	0.234		Not Significant
	Longer	58	60.70				

When grouped according to age and length of service, the computed p -values were higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as “not significant”. Thus, the hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference in the level of interpersonal skills of public elementary school heads in the area emotional intelligence skills according to age and length of service” was therefore “accepted”. This implies that age and length of service does not affect the level of interpersonal skills of public elementary school heads in terms of emotional intelligence skills. However, when grouped according to highest educational attainment, the computed Mann-Whitney U test was 1047.000 and the p -value was 0.003, it is lower than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as “significant”.

Thus, the hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference in the level of interpersonal skills of public elementary school heads in the area emotional intelligence skills according to highest educational attainment” was therefore “rejected”. This implies that highest educational attainment affects the level of interpersonal skills of public elementary school heads in terms of emotional intelligence skills. This also means that there is a difference in the opinion of teachers who have post graduate degrees than those who have none. This difference must be patched for an easier implementation of school projects. Badian (2019) conducted a study on the leadership practices of secondary school heads in relation to teachers’ performance in a medium-sized division in northern Negros Occidental. The study found that there was a significant relationship between the levels of School Heads’ leadership practices and the teachers’ performance. The researcher concluded that school heads’ leadership practices vary and to some level it affects teachers’ performance. The researcher recommended that the Schools Division Superintendent, the joint Chiefs of Curriculum and Instruction Division and School Governance and Operations Division be involved in yearly school heads’ calibration.

Table 14
Difference in the Level of Interpersonal Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in the Area Decision Making / Problem Solving According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
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Age	Younger	74	64.19	1975.000	0.772	Not Significant
	Older	55	66.09			
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	96	66.84	1470.500	0.334	0.05
	Higher	33	59.65			
Length of Service	Shorter	71	66.42	1958.000	0.628	Not Significant
	Longer	58	63.26			

When grouped according to age, highest educational attainment, and length of service, the computed p -values were higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant". Thus, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of interpersonal skills of public elementary school heads in the area problem solving according to age, highest educational attainment and length of service" was therefore "accepted". This implies that age, highest educational attainment and length of service does not affect the level of interpersonal skills of public elementary school heads in terms of problem solving. Villanueva (2021) assessed the leadership of school heads in the towns of Nueva Ecija in Central Philippines. The study was anchored on Republic Act No. 9155 otherwise known as the Governance of Basic Education Act. The result of the study revealed that school leaders' interpersonal, leadership, and supervisory skills were regarded as evident by both the school and their teachers. The inter-relationship of Supervisory Skills, Interpersonal Skills and Leadership Skills showed significant associations between the school head's decision making and their managerial skills in planning and organizing thereby concluding that School Heads' leadership was evident.

Conclusions:

The leadership skills of school heads are high particularly with the pursuance of Mission and Vision. This means that the respondents viewed school heads as competent and effective leaders who can initiate, sustain and achieve academic excellence. The supervisory skills of school heads are high, especially with written and verbal communication. The result implies that teachers showed highly satisfactory performance, a reflection of their commitment to effective instruction and student engagement. Their performance contributes significantly to student achievement and overall academic success, reinforcing the importance of continuous professional development and institutional support in maintaining high teaching standards. There was a significant difference in the level of interpersonal skills of public elementary School Heads in terms of emotional intelligence when grouped and compared according to their highest educational attainment. This means that their academic training of the respondents may have some influence on how they view school heads' emotional maturity at work. There was a significant difference in the level of leadership skills of public elementary school heads in the areas of pursuance of mission and vision, and in empowering teachers when grouped according to highest educational attainment. This means that respondents' view of their school heads' ability to lead are essentially influenced by their academic achievements. There was a significant difference in the level of supervisory skills of public elementary school heads particularly in the area of mentorship, when grouped and compared according to highest educational attainments. This implies that view of the respondents on the ability of school heads to mentor a teacher, or implement a mentoring program is influenced as well by their highest educational attainment. The results of the study indicate that the level of interpersonal skills of public elementary School Heads does not significantly impact the performance of teachers. This finding suggests that while interpersonal skills are an important aspect of leadership, other factors such as instructional support, professional development opportunities, and organizational culture may play a more substantial role in influencing teacher effectiveness. The absence of a strong correlation highlights the need for further research into additional variables that contribute to teacher performance and overall educational outcomes.

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